

Near-Field Spherical Scanning: Quiet-Zone Field Evaluation¹

R. H. Direen, M. H. Francis, and R. C. Wittmann

National Institute of Standards and Technology, Boulder, CO 80305,

Email: francis@boulder.nist.gov

1. Introduction

Determination of the illuminating electromagnetic fields within a test zone has long been of interest, for example, in the evaluation of compact-range performance. Recently, the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) has explored the use of an interior, near-field spherical scanning method for measuring this illumination [1], [2].

To test effectiveness, we have compared test-zone fields found by applying both the interior [1] and the (standard) exterior [3], near-field, spherical scanning techniques. In both techniques, the response is measured while moving a probe over the surface of a measurement sphere. In the interior method (Figure 1), the probe points radially outward to determine the fields interior to the sphere; all sources are assumed to be outside of the sphere. In the external spherical near-field scanning method (Figure 2), the probe points radially inward to determine the fields exterior to the sphere; sources in this case are interior to the sphere.

The interior approach has an advantage in that measurements are required only in the region of interest. The exterior approach can be impractical when the source antenna is very large as is frequently the case for compact ranges. On the other hand, the interior algorithm may suffer from poor conditioning due to probe insensitivity issues.

We compare the fields of a 46 cm Ku-band dish determined in a region where both the interior and exterior methods apply. To qualify the comparison, we provide preliminary estimates of measurement uncertainty.

2. Measurement and Data Reduction

For practical reasons, we use specially constructed $\mu = \pm 1$ probes [4]. At a given sample location $\mathbf{r} = r\hat{\mathbf{r}}$, measurements are made in two orientations separated by a 90° rotation of the probe about its axis. These measurements may be combined to form a vector probe response $\mathbf{w}'(\mathbf{r})/a_0$, where a_0 is the excitation. Although we suppress the details, proper normalization is necessary when absolute field comparisons are required.

The initial step is to construct the expansion

$$\frac{\mathbf{w}'(\mathbf{r})}{a_0} = \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{m=-n}^n [W_{nm}^1(r) \mathbf{X}_{nm}^1(\hat{\mathbf{r}}) + W_{nm}^2(r) \mathbf{X}_{nm}^2(\hat{\mathbf{r}})] \quad (1)$$

¹U.S. Government work not subject to U.S. Copyright

The coefficients W_{nm}^1 and W_{nm}^2 are determined using the orthogonality of the spherical harmonics \mathbf{X}_{nm}^i [3]. Practically, the summation on n must be truncated. For interior scanning, $N = N_i \sim kr_b$, where r_b is the radius of the interior measurement sphere. For exterior scanning, $N = N_e \sim kr_{min}$. Here r_{min} is the radius of the *minimum sphere*; that is, the radius of the smallest sphere, concentric with the measurement sphere, that completely encloses the source antenna. A measurement sphere of radius r_a will be larger than r_{min} for the exterior case. Data points are equispaced in θ and φ , with $\Delta\theta, \Delta\varphi < 2\pi/(2N + 1)$ in accordance with the sampling theorem.

In the interior case, the electric field is expanded in standing wave modes that are finite at the origin [1]

$$\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}) = a_0 \sum_{n=1}^{N_i} \sum_{m=-n}^n \left[v_{nm}^1 \mathbf{m}_{nm}^{(1)}(\mathbf{r}) + v_{nm}^2 \mathbf{n}_{nm}^{(1)}(\mathbf{r}) \right] \quad (2)$$

and, similarly, in the external case the field is expanded in outwardly traveling wave modes which satisfy the radiation condition [3]

$$\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}') = a_0 \sum_{n=1}^{N_e} \sum_{m=-n}^n \left[t_{nm}^1 \mathbf{m}_{nm}^{(3)}(\mathbf{r}') + t_{nm}^2 \mathbf{n}_{nm}^{(3)}(\mathbf{r}') \right] \quad (3)$$

Position vectors \mathbf{r} and $\mathbf{r}' = \mathbf{r} + \mathbf{r}_d$ are measured from the centers of respective measurement spheres that are separated by the displacement \mathbf{r}_d . The modes $\mathbf{m}_{nm}^{(1,3)}$ and $\mathbf{n}_{nm}^{(1,3)}$ are defined in [1] and [3]. Expansion coefficients are determined from

$$\begin{pmatrix} v_{nm}^1 \\ v_{nm}^2 \end{pmatrix} = \mathbf{M}_{inm}^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} W_{nm}^1 \\ W_{nm}^2 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \begin{pmatrix} t_{nm}^1 \\ t_{nm}^2 \end{pmatrix} = \mathbf{M}_{enm}^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} W_{nm}^1 \\ W_{nm}^2 \end{pmatrix} \quad (4)$$

The 2×2 matrices \mathbf{M}_{inm} and \mathbf{M}_{enm} , depend on the measurement radius and the known receiving function of the probe [1], [3]. There is no assumption that the probe measures components of the electric or magnetic field directly.

When $r_d > r_a + r_{min}$, either (2) or (3) can be used to compute the field in the test zone and this provides an opportunity for the comparison of measurement methods. The required software is available from the authors.

Our source antenna was a Ku-band dish, $r_{min} \approx 46$ cm. Exterior measurements were performed on a sphere, $r_a = 152$ cm, with $\Delta\varphi = \Delta\theta = 1^\circ$. Interior measurements were performed on a test zone, $r_b = 75$ cm, with $\Delta\varphi = \Delta\theta = 0.6^\circ$. The test zone was centered on the boresite of the dish at $r_d = 439$ cm.

3. Results

Figures 3-5 show $\|\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r})\|$ for the three principal cuts within the overlap region. In each figure, the solid line corresponds to the exterior measurement; the dashed line corresponds to the interior measurement.

Uncertainties of the interior measurement are illustrated by the shaded region and uncertainty bars. (The exterior measurement uncertainties are smaller than the interior case and are not plotted here.) The shaded region corresponds to the uncertainty due to noise [2]; the uncertainty bars correspond to uncertainties due to multiple reflections between the dish and probe. Our analysis is based on the work of Newell [5] and Hansen [4]. Table 1 indicates uncertainties for the exterior measurements. If a source considered by [4] or [5] is not shown, the uncertainty due to that source is estimated to be less than 0.1 dB. Test-zone measurements made with both interior and exterior spherical scanning techniques agree to within expected uncertainties. For the interior measurement, the multiple reflection uncertainty estimate was based on a crude simulation. Further study may lead to improvement of these preliminary estimates.

4. Conclusion

The interior spherical scanning method can be used to quantify the fields incident on a test zone. The method is potentially useful in evaluating anechoic chamber and compact range performance.

References

- [1] Wittmann, R. C., "Spherical near-field scanning: Determining the incident field near a rotatable probe," *1990 IEEE Antennas and Propagation Symposium Digest*, pp. 224-227, May 7-11, 1990.
- [2] Direen, R. H., Wittmann, R. C., and Francis, M. H. "Near-Field Spherical Scanning: Uncertainties In Test-Zone Field Measurements," *Proc. AMTA*, pp. 322-325, Nov. 2008.
- [3] Francis, M. H., and R. C. Wittmann, Chapter 19 in C. A. Balanis, ed., *Modern Antenna Handbook*. New York: Wiley, 2008.
- [4] Hansen, J. E., *Spherical Near-field Antenna Measurements*, Chap. 6, Peter Peregrinus Ltd., 1988.
- [5] Newell, A. C., "Error Analysis Techniques for Planar Near-Field Measurements," *IEEE Trans. Antennas Propagat.*, vol. AP-36, no. 6, pp. 754-768, June 1988.

Table 1 Relative pattern uncertainties for the external case (coverage factor of 2).

Uncertainty Source (relative to peak) of:	Uncertainty (dB) at pattern levels			
	0 dB	-5 dB	-10 dB	-15 dB
Nonlinearity	0	±0.1	±0.1	±0.2
Noise	±0.1	±0.1	±0.1	±0.2
Probe pattern	±0.1	±0.1	±0.1	±0.1
Multiple reflections	±0.3	±0.3	±0.4	±0.5
Root sum square	±0.3	±0.3	±0.4	±0.6

Figure 1: Interior, near-field, spherical scanning.

Figure 3: The radial cut, corresponding to the x axis, along which the power drops off as $1/r^2$. Interior (dashed), exterior (solid).

Figure 2: Exterior, near-field, spherical scanning.

Figure 4: Horizontal cut.

Figure 5: Vertical cut.